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The methodological basis of teaching English Writing in Secondary Schools

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Annotation: The article is to learn and analysis of main principles of teaching written speech as well as dialogue and monologue speech and listening of Foreign Language Teaching.

Key words: techniques and materials, language intimation, knowledge, target, factors, cognitive processes, coherent narrations, discourse, hesitation

Many teachers consider the beginning level of language intimation to be the most challenging. Since students at this level have little or no prior knowledge of the target language, the teacher (and accompanying techniques and materials) becomes a central determiner in whether students accomplish their goals. This can also be the most tangibly rewarding level for a teacher because the growth of students' proficiency is apparent in a matter of a few weeks.

At the beginning or even false-beginning level, your students have very little language "behind" them. You may therefore be tempted to go along with the popular misconception that the target language cannot be taught directly, that you will have to resort to a good deal of talking "about" the second language in the students' native language. Such is clearly not the case, as beginning language courses have demonstrated for many decades. But you do have to keep in mind that your students' capacity for taking in and retaining new words, structures, and concepts is limited. Foremost on your mind as a teacher should be the presentation of material in simple segments that don't overwhelm your students. Remember, they are just barely beginning!

The following 10 factors and the words of advice accompanying each will help you to formulate an approach to teaching beginners. As you adopt a theoretical stance on each factor, you will be able to design classroom techniques that are consistent with your approach.

In those first few days and even weeks of language learning, virtually all of the **students'** processing with respect to the second language itself is in a focal, controlled (for a review of McLaughlin's cognitive processes and classroom applications). Therefore, you can expect to engage in plenty of competition of a limited number of words, phrases, and sentences. Don't become if a considerable period of time goes by with little change in these learning modes. Lived in the first few days of class, however, you can coax your students into the time peripheral processing by getting them to use practiced language for genuinely meaningful purposes. For example, getting information from a classmate whom a student does not know will require using newly learned language ("What's your name?" "Where do you live?"), but with a focus on the purposes to which the language is put, not on the forms of language. The forms themselves, although still controlled (limited in capacity), nevertheless move into a peripheral mode as students become immersed in the task of seeking genuine information.

Beginning students are highly dependent on the teacher for models of language, and so a teacher-centered or teacher-fronted classroom is appropriate for some of your classroom time. Students are able to initiate few questions and comments, so it is your responsibility to "keep the ball rolling." Still, your beginning level classes need not be devoid of a modicum of student-centered work. Pair work and group work are effective techniques for taking students' focus off you as the center of attention and for getting them into an interactive frame of mind even at the most beginning level.

It follows that the degree of control of classroom time also leans strongly in the direction of the teacher at the beginning levels. In a second language context where instruction is carried out in the target language, virtually all of your class time will be teacher-controlled. Since students have no means, in the second language anyway, of controlling the class period, the onus is on you to plan topics, activity types, time-on-task, etc. As students gain in their proficiency, they will be able to initiate questions and comments of their own that may then occasionally shift the locus of control. In a foreign language situation, where your students speak the same native language (and you speak it as well), some negotiation might be possible in the native language, allowing for a small amount of student control.

Superior Speakers at the Superior level are able to communicate in the language fluently in order to participate fully and effectively in conversations on a variety of

topics in formal and informal settings from both concrete and abstract perspectives. They discuss their interests and special fields of competence, explain complex in detail, and provide lengthy and coherent narrations, all with ease, fluency, and accuracy. They explain their opinions on a number of topics of importance to them, such as social and political issues, and provide structured argument to support their opinions. They are able to construct and develop hypotheses to explore alternative possibilities. When appropriate, they use extended discourse without unnaturally lengthy hesitation to make their point, even when engaged in abstract elaborations. Such discourse, while coherent, may still be influenced by the Superior speakers' **own** language patterns, rather than those of the target language.

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